

Active MEMS for Exploration of Hair Cell Dynamics

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Abstract. Historically, improved understanding of auditory dynamics has mainly been approached in two ways: first, through improvement in experimental techniques for measuring oscillating parts inside the cochlea and/or in the organ of Corti such as e.g. hair cell and bundle motions, and second, through theoretical modeling and analysis which encapsulates some experimentally observed phenomena on a macroscopic scale. However, in-vitro and in-vivo studies are challenging and costly, as these require the navigation of nano-scale motions of delicate, coupled hair bundle structures in complex ionic, electrical, and mechanical environments which make it difficult to dissect and extricate underlying mechanisms of experimentally observed hair bundle activities. In this work we propose a third approach. An experimental approach using active micro-electromechanical system (MEMS) devices offers a controlled and systematic means of further investigating cause, effect, and control of e.g. auditory Hopf dynamics which will complement existing biophysical experimentation. We demonstrate that an active mechano-electrical transduction process which occurs in hair cell bundles can be artificially realized in an actively operated MEMS resonator. The active MEMS consists of a composite micro-beam with coupled thermal actuation and piezoelectric sensing capability which is modulated using linear feedback control. Using a combination of reduced-order modelling, computational analysis, and experimental investigations, we explore the MEMS' rich dynamic bifurcation landscape, and discuss its compressive amplification properties across pre- and post-Hopf parameter regimes. With this novel active MEMS-based approach, we would like to engage in existing scientific discussions and make meaningful contributions to yet unsolved mechanisms of hearing.

INTRODUCTION

Inspired by scientists' ongoing research efforts towards the mechanics of hearing^{4,10,18,23,27,30} and the ever-growing need for technological solutions for the hearing impaired, we have recently begun tailoring our ongoing research efforts on nonlinear, active, coupled oscillators of microelectromechanical systems (MEMS)^{11,12,20,21,31} to the field of dynamics of the human hearing process^{14,24–26,29}.

Compressive amplification and sharp frequency tuning are closely associated with the ability of the human ear to operate over a remarkably broad dynamic range^{15,16,30}. There is strong scholarly evidence to suggest that observed nonlinear sound processing features are the result of an underlying Hopf dynamics (self-excited resonators) in the hair cell bundles^{1,16,22}. Hopf dynamics in the auditory system is typically attributed to coupled sensing and actuation functionalities in the hair cells, where active motile processes, including Ca^{2+} -dependent channel re-closure, somatic electro-motility, and myosin-based adaptation, depend on the magnitude of hair bundle deflection^{7–9,28}. Experts in the field continue to encourage novel contributions towards the development of a general theory for critical oscillators in hair cells and cochlea^{18,28}. One of the underlying questions to be answered is the question related to the origins of the observed Hopf dynamics. Current knowledge about the existence of Hopf dynamics in the human hearing process is revealed from in-vivo experiments^{16,17,30}, theoretical lumped-mass approaches and macro-scale experiments focusing on the dynamics including feedback mechanisms²². Other works also include the fluid-structure interaction and travelling wave in the cochlea^{1,10}, further strengthening that underlying Hopf dynamics are responsible for explaining key features of the human hearing process.

Gutschmidt and Lenci¹³ have recently investigated sufficient and necessary conditions for the existence of Hopf dynamics in MEMS resonators. Although generally well known, particularly in the nonlinear dynamics research community, we have derived a generalized Hopf condition for the most commonly used MEMS models and systems. We found that a necessary condition for a MEMS system to undergo Hopf dynamics is to be coupled, thus $n \geq 3$ with n being the number of state variables. The sufficient condition would then be one of the following three options: i) a MEMS resonator operated with either integrated actuator or sensor mechanism, ii) MEMS with implementation of a digital control mechanism or iii) coupling of the MEMS structure to any other physics field as e.g. an operation in fluid¹³. All these cases would lead to Hopf dynamics of the system in mathematical terms, namely, that a purely imaginary pair of eigenvalues exists while all other eigenvalues are real and non-zero³². To continue with this systematic

approach, we have since begun to study Hopf dynamics in active MEMS via i) feedback control mechanism and ii) fluid interaction of hair bundles^{2,3}.

The most commonly talked about “energy source” (necessary condition) concerning the hearing mechanism is referred to local chemical processes such as ion channels⁷⁻⁹. Inspired by ongoing efforts we introduce an active MEMS system which has Hopf-capability and whose rich dynamic landscape promises meaningful insights for further investigating the mechanics of hearing. The MEMS system can be compared to being an equivalent electro-mechanical transducer that converts acoustic pressure stimuli into electric output signals. We briefly introduce the active MEMS oscillator and emphasise on the parameter range where the dynamics transitions from quiescence to a self-sustained limit-cycle. In this work we discuss the dynamic behaviour of the active MEMS device for three distinct amplification scenarios, namely that of linear, nonlinear-compressive, and amplitude-locking. Furthermore, we show that modulation of equivalent to biophysical parameters such as extra- and intracellular Ca^{2+} concentrations, membrane resting potential, elastic load stiffness, and external sound stimuli, tune the system between these three different amplification properties, further encouraging that the MEMS approach would be a valuable independent way of i) studying the mechanics of hearing and ii) developing associated technologies to help people with hearing impairment or loss.

THE ACTIVE MEMS RESONATOR: REAL AND MODEL

More than 20 years ago, Rangelow et al.¹⁹ invented a MEMS probe (see Fig. 1) for developing and advancing performance metrics in atomic force microscopy (AFM). The design and functionality of these MEMS resonators are unique for their integrated sensing and actuation capabilities. Within our collaboration with Rangelow et al. over the last 15+ years we have come to appreciate this smart MEMS device for its wide spectrum of other applications, including sensors, manipulators and actuators, and also for the noticeably richer dynamic landscape, typically absent in other comparable MEMS oscillators which are passively operated. Figure 1 depicts the composite MEMS cantilever

FIGURE 1. Composite MEMS cantilever with integrated actuation and sensing mechanisms; a) iso-view of a CAD model; b) side view of the CAD model (different scale) for actuated top layer; c) SEM image with JEOL JSM-IT300.

for which we have previously derived a comprehensive model which includes complexities such as its composite structure, material properties and dimensions of layers, position of the neutral axis, differences of regions along the length of the beam, as well as sensor and actuator principles³¹. In more recent work we have also developed a first simple heat transfer model with which we investigate the heat flow across the thickness of the composite structure with respect to periodicity and duty cycles⁵. In this work we consider the bending motion in its first fundamental resonance, thermally induced by means of the bi-morph effect (see Fig. 1b). Its tip deflection is measured by an integrated piezo-resistive sensor near the base. Key features of the dynamic behaviour are captured by the following reduced-order model

$$\ddot{q}_w + \delta \dot{q}_w + q_w - \alpha q_\theta = \kappa(\tau), \quad (1a)$$

$$\dot{q}_\theta + \beta q_\theta = \gamma u(\tau)^2, \quad (1b)$$

which is deduced from the originally derived governing equations of the composite MEMS system by Roeser et al.³¹. q_w and q_θ in Eq. (1) are the nondimensionalised mechanical and thermal variables of the system representing the modal deflection of the cantilever and the response of temperature difference, respectively. Parameters α , β , γ , δ are classic integration constants originating from a modified Ritz discretization³¹, wherein δ is related to the damping.

The coupling between the mechanical and thermal systems is determined by the strength of the coupling parameter α . The system can either be actuated by the integrated Joule heating mechanism represented by the current and Ohm's law $i(\tau) = u(\tau)/R$ (R being the electrical resistance hidden in γ and $u(\tau)$ is the voltage) or by an external periodic stimulus $\kappa_{ext}(\tau)$ such as for example an acoustic signal or piezo-base excitation. In this work we choose the integrated thermal actuator for implementing the feedback mechanism $u(\tau) = \tanh(aq_w + b)$, where b is an off-set voltage with which to control equilibrium states and a is the feedback strength, just as Joyce et al.²² have conducted for a macro-scale system. The external stimulus $\kappa(\tau)$ in the experiment is implemented via a piezo-actuator (PI PL022.3x) placed near the base of the MEMS. While the system equations (1) represent the theoretical model of the MEMS system, a more complete model for investigating an experimentally equivalent system would also include several filter dynamics, thus extending Eqs. (1) to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{q}_w \\ \dot{q}_w \\ \dot{q}_\theta \\ \dot{u} \\ \dot{q}_h \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} q_w \\ -q_w - \delta \dot{q}_w + \alpha q_\theta + \kappa(\tau) \\ -\beta q_\theta + \gamma u^2 \\ -\omega_l(u - \tanh(aq_h + b)) \\ -\omega_h q_h + \nu \dot{q}_w \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

The first three lines in (2) represent the dynamics of the structure in state-space form as per (1), where the state vector is $\mathbf{q} = [q_w, \dot{q}_w, q_\theta, u, q_h]^T$, associated with the unfiltered deflection and velocity of the MEMS structure, the temperature difference, the voltage, and the filtered deflection of the cantilever. Lines four and five represent the feedback controller equation coupled to low-pass and high-pass filters, respectively. Latter are necessary entries for successful experimental implementation and investigations of the system. Parameters ν , ω_l and ω_h are the filter gain, and cut-off frequencies for low and high-pass filters, respectively. Note, that the governing equations are presented in non-dimensionalised form, with τ being the unitless time.

The existence of Hopf dynamics is determined from the roots of the linearized system about its equilibria. Thus, from the Jacobian matrix of (1) it can readily be observed that the system equations (1) lead to the following Hopf condition¹³

$$\alpha \varepsilon = -\delta(\beta^2 + \beta \delta + 1), \quad (3)$$

which have the following associated roots

$$\lambda_1 = -(\beta + \delta), \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda_{2,3} = \pm i \sqrt{\beta \delta + 1}. \quad (5)$$

Therefore, for $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta > 0$ and for tuples of the control parameters $[\text{gain}, \text{offset}] = [\pm a, \mp b]$, the system undergoes Hopf dynamics. The parameter ε in (3) is abbreviated as $\varepsilon = (2\gamma a \tanh b) / \cosh b^2$ or for better observance of dominating parameters in linearised form $\varepsilon = 2\gamma \cdot a \cdot b$. The Hopf condition for the system with filters (2), although more complex, looks similar in its concept.

COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS

While the analysis presented here mainly focuses on the active dynamics, we also consider its passive behaviour for sake of comparison and discussion. All analyses are following standard methods of nonlinear dynamics, including time and frequency domain methods, continuation methods as well as bifurcation and stability maps. Furthermore, we initially refer to existing work about dynamic aspects of this MEMS resonator to be able to keep the focus of this work on new findings relevant to the Hopf dynamics. For more details on equilibria and bifurcation landscape of the MEMS system with and without filter dynamics the reader is referred to Lam et al.²⁴ and Hayashi et al.¹⁴.

Amplitude Dynamics and Bifurcation Landscape

Following on from previously obtained insights about equilibria and parameter regions of Hopf bifurcations^{14,24}, we conduct the analyses (computational and experimental) near one of these parameter sets, namely for

$$\Lambda = [\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \hat{\kappa}, \nu, \omega_l, \omega_h, a, b] = [0.52, 0.0133, 0.0624, 0.012, \hat{\kappa}, 1, 2, 0.0714, a, -0.1].$$

FIGURE 2. Computational results of MEMS system with filters (2) for varying strengths of control gain a ; a) equilibria; b) Hopf dynamics; c) superposed solutions and numerical validations of solution branches of equilibria and Hopf in a)+b) marked in blue; purple square marker - Hopf bifurcation $a_H = 1.89$; purple line is distinguishing between pre- and post-Hopf behaviours (respectively shaded in grey and blue in c)); solid lines - stable; dashed lines - unstable; results modified from Hayashi et al.¹⁴.

FIGURE 3. Hopf dynamic landscape of the filtered system (2) in the frequency domain for varying control strengths a ; amplitude response \hat{q}_h for $[\hat{k}, b] = [1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}, -0.1]$; solid lines - stable, dashed lines - unstable; red curves of $\eta = 1$ plane are representatives of curves in Fig. 2c); the purple Hopf plane distinguishes between pre- and post-Hopf parameter regions.

Consider the dynamic landscape as depicted in Figure 2, which represents equilibria, Hopf- and superposed dynamic solutions of system (2) for varying strengths of the control gain a and external harmonic stimulus \hat{k} . In the absence of external stimulus the system remains stationary for any control strength $a < a_H$, see Figs. 2a)+b). No oscillations occur for the autonomous system until the onset of the Hopf dynamics at the bifurcation $a = a_H$, see purple markers and lines in Figs. 2a)+b). For $a \geq a_H$ the former constant equilibria lose stability and a new stable equilibrium branch is born (Fig. 2a)) due to self-excited oscillation (Fig. 2b)). Numerical time integration simulations validate the onset of Hopf dynamics including oscillation amplitudes (square markers).

In the presence of an external excitation (Fig. 2c)), the system experiences three significantly different amplification properties. With the control mechanism turned off, $a = 0$, the system is operated passively and we observe classic resonance behaviour. We present in Fig. 2c) the bifurcation diagram for constant tuning ratio ($\eta = 1$) and varying stimulus strengths over a range of feedback gains a . Note that resonance peaks vary (see Fig. 3) with a and \hat{k} . For control gains $0 < a < a_H$ (grey-shaded region in Fig. 2c)), compressive amplification properties can readily be

observed, also presented in Lam et al.²⁴ (Figs.7 and 8). Beyond the onset of Hopf, for $a > a_H$ (blue-shaded region), we observe that i) only solution branches that are larger in amplitude than that of the Hopf backbone curve (blue dotted line) are stable and that ii) the system for low external stimuli responds with the Hopf amplitude according to Fig. 2b). (The blue dotted line in Fig. 2c) is the blue solid line in Fig. 2b). Numerical time integration simulations further validate pre- and post-Hopf regions.

Further investigations of the dynamics in the post-Hopf region (shaded region in blue, Fig. 2 c)) yield frequency response curves for which additional bifurcations (Fig. 3) determine the stability of solution branches in that region. For example, at $a = 4$ two Neimark-Sacker (NS) bifurcation points occur, rendering the upper solution branch stable while the lower branches on both sides become unstable. Further along $a > 6$, additional pairs of saddle node (SN) bifurcations occur, giving rise to co-existing unstable solutions. At the ‘‘cusp’’ of both NS points i.e. $a > 9$ we observe isola-dynamics in the frequency domain, whereas the upper branch being stable and the lower unstable.

Frequency Entrainment

Apart from apparently nonlinear amplification properties pre-Hopf, responses of the actively operated MEMS system are comparable to that of their passively operated counterparts. Responses are periodic with externally imposed operation frequency. In the post-Hopf parameter region, the stability of solutions is very sensitive to the strength of the input strength $\hat{\kappa}$. For input strengths that produce a response with amplitudes larger than the Hopf amplitudes of the autonomous system, the entire frequency response is initially stable, which marks the region between $a = a_H$ and at which the NS bifurcations first occur (see Fig. 3). At the appearance of the first pair of NS points and also the SN further along, the system is characterized by an upper stable branch and two co-existing side branches. The same stability of branches is also observed for the isola-dynamics region beyond the cusp of the NS pair. Results in Fig. 4 are generated from numerical and experimental time responses subject to different excitation frequencies presenting their Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), where colored markers represent response peaks, with yellow indicating high and blue indicating low amplitude maxima. Associated frequencies are that of the Hopf (horizontal) and resonance (diagonal) dynamics, respectively. In the region where Hopf and resonance frequencies become similar (shaded area), the system oscillates with only the excitation frequency and the Hopf frequency disappears. The time response is periodic. This phenomena is known as frequency entrainment which is also observed in many other systems dominated by Hopf dynamics (e.g. MEMS subject to laser interference⁶).

For input strengths to which the system’s response amplitude is smaller than that of the Hopf amplitude, the system’s dynamics transitions much faster to the isola-dynamics i.e. isola-dynamics appear for much lower values of the control gain a . Note, that for lower input signals Fig. 2c) does not show isola-dynamics, as these appear slightly away from the $\eta = 1$ cross-section. Stable top branch solutions are characterised by periodic oscillations of self-excited amplitudes and excitation frequency.

FIGURE 4. Frequency entrainment in simulation (a) and experiment (b). Response frequency versus excitation frequency. Colors refer to levels of response amplitudes at resonance, yellow-high and blue-low. Diagonal peaks refer to resonance frequencies and horizontally aligned peaks to limit cycle frequency (Hopf). Shaded areas highlight region of frequency entrainment.

Experiments are conducted with our recently developed MEMS test set-up¹⁴. Parameters are chosen to compare results qualitatively. Figure 4b) is generated from multiple experiments varying the excitation frequency and measuring the deflection of the MEMS structure as responses. The actuation is implemented by a piezo actuator placed at the base of the MEMS cantilever, and the deflections of the MEMS device are measured by the integrated piezo-resistive sensor. The feedback control is implemented using an in-house developed field programmable gate array (FPGA) controller which activates the integrated heating actuator of the MEMS device. Further details about the experimental set-up are documented in Hayashi et al.¹⁴. The amplitude of the FFT is presented as a scatter plot, where yellow and blue markers are high and low peaks in the FFT. As revealed through the computational analysis, also experimental investigations confirm the frequency entrainment (shaded region) for a narrow frequency range at which the Hopf frequency disappears and the system response with only the resonance frequency.

CONCLUSION

In this work we have presented qualitative Hopf dynamics of an actively operated MEMS device. We have briefly introduced a simple but suitable model of the MEMS structure, shown sufficient and necessary conditions for the existence of Hopf dynamics in MEMS, and conducted computational and experimental analysis pre- and post-Hopf bifurcation. Although the focus of this work has not been towards matching results quantitatively, both approaches confirm underlying physics of this active MEMS system. We have performed the analysis in three parameter regions (varying the control gain) at which the amplification properties are distinctively different. For $a = 0$ we observe the classic resonance behaviour of a passively operated MEMS, pre-Hopf ($0 < a < a_H$) the system shows compressive amplification properties, and post-Hopf ($a \geq a_H$) one of the main characteristics is frequency entrainment. Given these computational and experimental results are qualitatively consistent, i) the broader mechanics of hearing research community has an additional research tool at its disposal to systematically investigate unresolved questions, and ii) the engineering community can further advance related technologies to benefit people with hearing loss.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Dolores Bozovic] This work provides a very nice complement to hair cell experiments, in that it allows Hopf bifurcation dynamics to be studied in an artificial system, with known and controllable parameters. I think it a very promising direction, and different from other studies in the field. Is the experimental system scalable? Specifically, it would be very interesting to create a 'tonotopic' array, to model the cochlea, then a uniformly distributed array, to model the sacculus, etc. I realize that MEMS devices are very challenging to fabricate, but perhaps scaling up from one to many is doable.

[Stefanie Gutschmidt] The experimental system is definitely scalable. The fabrication of a passively operated tonotopic-like devices have successfully been demonstrated in literature, even for the development of cochlear implants. An actively driven device therefore does not pose a challenge given the current state of MEMS manufacturing.

[Kalpan Ved] In the abstract you have mentioned "The active MEMS consists of thermal actuation and piezoelectric sensing" However, in the model and figures, you have mentioned piezo-resistive sensing. Maybe you meant piezo-resistive in this case.

[Stefanie Gutschmidt] Thank you. Yes, the original abstract which we first submitted had this terminology wrong. It is corrected in the article.

[Kalpan Ved] You have added a low-pass filter in your model equation set. What is the purpose of adding a low-pass filter? Have you also added a low pass filter in your experimental setup?

[Stefanie Gutschmidt] The low-pass filter was added to the model to match the experimental system. The purpose of the low-pass filter in the experimental system is to remove the high-frequency noise emitted by the controller. Its cutoff frequency was designed for 200 kHz.

[Kalpan Ved] Its quite interesting to see an entrainment in the range of 500 Hz (99.5 kHz - 100 kHz). What are the Q factors of your MEMS cantilever?

[Stefanie Gutschmidt] We do not seem to observe the same thing. Figure 4b) suggests a range of > 500 Hz (98.5-99.7 kHz). We have not quantitatively investigated the entrainment region. We only observe its existence for when the limit cycle frequency is close to that of the forcing frequency. However, we do observe that this entrainment region is influenced by control tuples $[a, b]$ as well as the strength of the stimulus $\hat{\kappa}$.

[John B Allen] (Comment) I would call this a cochlear amplifier. You have finally discovered the cochlear amplifier - quantified. And you have got my vote. I would put money on it.

[Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh] Martin Golubitsky also examined the responses to large forces and saw these isola. Comparing to his work I think it's along that. I saw that some of your diagrams show a supercritical bifurcation while in an earlier diagram it was a subcritical bifurcation. So I was trying to figure out, is it always supercritical what you are looking at or does it depend on which parameter you are picking?

[Stefanie Gutschmidt] The existence of isola dynamics mainly seem to depend on the strength of the external stimulus. The sub- or supercritical Hopf bifurcation behaviour depends on the choice of parameters. In our work it is the DC-offset parameter of the controller. For very large values of b we observe subcritical, while for smaller values we see a supercritical Hopf characteristic.